

The "Sarapeion" of Thessalonica

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The so-called Serapeum of Thessalonica was not dedicated only to Serapis, nor has this name survived through the ancient sources; the name Serapeum was given by the researchers who excavated the site in the early 20th century and has survived ever since. It consists of at least four buildings: a small temple with a rectangular plan, another small temple in antis or prostyle with a crypt, and some other auxiliary spaces. The large number of statues and inscriptions suggests that the sanctuary hosted the cult of the Isiac family but also other deities such as Aphrodite, Athena, Pan. All these artifacts are a result of many chronological phases. During its five centuries of use, buildings were constructed, and probably buildings were reused for a different purpose. The different forms of deities worshiped in the sanctuary bear evidence of a vivid cult that involved numerous people: locals, Egyptians, Roman negotiatores, etc. They also reflect a strong network of religious connectivity between Thessalonica and other sites in the Aegean such as Delos, but also between Thessalonica and inland sites, such as Stobi.

Date Range: 210 BCE - 300 CE

Region: Thessalonica

Region tags: Europe, Southern Europe, Greece, Eastern Europe, Macedonia

The city was created in the Hellenistic times and has been inhabited throughout the centuries, providing an important port for the region.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Makaronas, C. 1940. "Χρονικά Αρχαιολογικά." Μακεδονικά 1: 464–465.
- Source 2: Steimle, C. 2002. "Neue Erkenntnisse zum Heiligtum der Ägyptischen Götter in Thessaloniki. Ein unveröffentlichtes Tagebuch des Archäologen Hans Von Schoenebeck." Αρχαιολογικό Έργο στη Μακεδονία και Θράκη 16: 291–306.
- Source 3: Steimle, C. 2008. Religion im römischen Thessaloniki. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://users.sch.gr/ipap/Ellinikos_Politismos/Sarapeio/Sarapeio.htm
- Source 1 Description: University essay on the sanctuary
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.amth.gr/exhibitions/exhibit-of-the-month/agalmatio-afroditis-omonoias-apo-iero-ton-aigyption-theon-sarapeio>
- Source 2 Description: Statue of the sanctuary at the Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki
- Source 1 URL: http://users.sch.gr/ipap/Ellinikos_Politismos/Sarapeio/Sarapeio.htm
- Source 1 Description: University essay on the sanctuary
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.amth.gr/exhibitions/exhibit-of-the-month/agalmatio-afroditis-omonoias-apo-iero-ton-aigyption-theon-sarapeio>
- Source 2 Description: Statue of the sanctuary at the Archaeological Museum of Thessaloniki

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1920-1921, 1938-1939

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Rescue excavation for the urban renewal of the area

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: The sanctuary was situated close to the port of the city

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: It was incorporated into the urban plan of the city, next to important roads leading to the city gates and the port

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The area where the sanctuary was situated has been characterized as the "religious area" of the city, probably hosting the sanctuary of Dionysus and an Archaic temple moved there during the Roman times.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: At least four buildings were unearthed during the various excavations: two small buildings and some other auxiliary spaces.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: A crypt under one of the two small temples

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not sure, they probably belong to different construction stages within the range of the five centuries of use of the space

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: Parts of it were destroyed and parts of it survived until the 20th century.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: Today nothing survives from the architectural remains unearthed during the excavations

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Isis, Serapis, Horus, Harpocrates, Osiris, Anubis but also Aphrodite, Athena, Hecate, Pan, Telesphoros

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Isis, Serapis, Horus, Harpocrates, Osiris, Anubis but also Aphrodite, Athena, Hecate, Pan, Telesphoros

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some altars or buildings were consecrated by specific families or people but in general, this is something that cannot be attested for the whole sanctuary.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: It was not sponsored but there were royal decrees that suggested how to manage the income of the sanctuary

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Notes: There are many dedications that show this relation between the devotees and the deities, mainly Isis, whom they thank for fulfilling a wish.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Notes: The excavations have revealed only part of the complex, in different excavation seasons, and the precinct of the sanctuary is not known. The four above mentioned structures have been attributed to the sanctuary but we should be cautious about that as there is no clear evidence on the limits of the sanctuary nor a plan with all buildings survives from the time of the excavation.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: One of the two temples was a small apsidal temple in antis or prostyle with and a staircase that lead to a crypt.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 88

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: One temple was made by walls of rubble masonry and the other was made by a typically Roman masonry with stones held together by mortar and interrupted by three layers of bricks.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Bricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

Notes: There is only one architectural fragment coming from the area of the sanctuary, which is still preserved today. It is a marble monolithic angular part of the entablature of ionic type. The front view is shaped as a pediment with a ledge, while the side view is decorated with two lion-headed gutters. Its dimensions suggest that it came from a small building but further identification with the few known structures is impossible.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The floor of the apsis temple was paved with marble cut in small irregular pieces of multi-colored slabs, forming a decoration of geometric designs.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There were a lot of dedications such as altars, marble slabs, or statues

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are at least 8 statues representing the Isiac deities (three of Isis, two of Serapis, one of Anubis, two of Harpocrates). There are also two representations of Aphrodite, one of Athena, one of Hecate, one of Pan and one of Telesphoros.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There is a small sphinx of black basalt

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are representations of priests and priestesses, probably one μελανηφόρος. Also, a relief of a young man, a donor who would bring a small animal as an offering to the sanctuary.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There is a relief of a young man preserved in eight pieces. This young man

would be a donor who would bring a small animal as an offering to the sanctuary, as he is holding it in his hands. It is difficult to determine what kind of animal it was due to its state of preservation. It could be poultry as it was a common offering to the Isiac deities.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A small sphinx of black basalt.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The excavations have brought to light at least 78 inscriptions which would decorate various parts of the sanctuary.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Even though there are a large number of sculptures that have survived it is not possible to determine which one of these was a cult statue.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Isis, Serapis, Harpocrates, Anubis but also Aphrodite, Athena, Hecate, Pan, Telesphoros

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Of priests and of devotees.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NO

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Reliefs representing footprints and ears, both as signs of commemoration of a fulfillment of a vow. The gods appeared and left their footprints in one case, while in the other the gods heard and fulfilled the wish.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: There are inscriptions that commemorate a special event regarding the relationship of the devotee with the divinity. There is also a narrative of how Serapis appeared in a dream of a certain man and asked him to propagate the cult in a city, Opus, of Central Greece. There is a fragmented aretalogy. There are inscriptions that commemorate donations to the sanctuary and the gods.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: A small sphinx of black basalt.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The gods Isis, Serapis, Harpocrates, Anubis

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Priests and devotees

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: The appearance of Serapis in a dream of a certain man in order to give him the order to propagate his cult in the city of Opus, in Central Greece.

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The dream of Ξεναίνετος is indicative: A certain Ξεναίνετος came from the city of Opus to the sanctuary of Thessalonica, where Serapis paid him a nocturnal visit and ordered him to find one of his fellow citizens, called Εὐρύνομος, and tell him that the god was charging him with the reception of Serapis and Isis in his city. Serapis announced that he would leave a letter with instructions to deliver it to Εὐρύνομος. When Ξεναίνετος woke up, he was amazed, but reluctant, since Εὐρύνομος was his political adversary. Consequently, for some time he defied the orders of Serapis. Then the god appeared to him again and ordered him to obey. After hearing the words of Ξεναίνετος and after reading the message from the god, Εὐρύνομος accepted the deities in the city.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: It would be in antiquity, but not anymore.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Notes: Nonetheless, one of the two temples had a crypt which kept concealed a Herma represented as a bearded figure. There is no certain information why it was found there and who this bearded figure might be.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Probably yes, in specific events

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Probably yes, in specific events

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Probably poultry

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: For this reason, there were people, holding the office of νεωκόρος, who would be charged with this duty.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Yes [specify]: Normally yes, the only indirect evidence from the sanctuary is the relief representing a young man bringing an animal as a gift to the gods.

- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No

- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - No

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes

Notes: There is an inscription that reveals that a three-membered family donated earrings of value that were used to adorn a statue of the goddess. Interestingly, inventories of jewels dedicated to Isiac contexts are rare in the Graeco-Roman world

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: There are people bearing specific titles, such as the νεωκόρος, who would be in charge of specific activities.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions suggest that along its five centuries of use the sanctuary received donations of new buildings and reconstructions of old ones.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The priest, the νεωκόρος, and perhaps other offices as well would have an annual - or determined - liturgy. After that period, someone else would be appointed with the same role.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Notes: Nonetheless, it is very common that people visit the sanctuary in order to thank Isis and the other gods.

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Yes

Notes: Isis, among others, protected women giving birth. This is the reason Isis is known in the sanctuary with the epithet Isis Lochia and there is an important number of dedications offered by women.

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The location of the sanctuary, close to the port and close to one of the city's gates might suggest such a rule, although it cannot be proven.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Probably yes. There is an inscription that indicates the presence of an association where the people involved would dine together.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: The Navigium Isidis and the Inventio Osiridis would be probably celebrated.

Frequency of festivals

– specify: Yearly

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Only initiates

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Some festivals would include only initiates while others, such as the Navigium Isidis which would follow the route from the sanctuary to the port, would be seen by everybody and all people were free to join the procession.

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Field doesn't know

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: -

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: It would be included in some festivals

Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Notes: Probabaly

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of a statuette of Telesphoros, the presence of Isis as Isis Lochia and the abundance of thanksgiving offerings all suggest that the deities in the sanctuary would serve a healing purpose as well.

Incubation

– Field doesn't know

Healing magic

– Field doesn't know

Cleansing

– Field doesn't know

Offerings of models of body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Expiation

– Field doesn't know

Other

– Other [specify]: No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Rituals would consist of adorning the cult statue, reading out loud the aretologies of Isis, offering gifts to the gods. They would also consist of processions taking place once a year. It is probable that the Navigium Isidis would take place, a procession that would end to the port, inaugurating the new navigation season, every 5th of March. The inscriptions suggesting a strong presence of Osiris in the sanctuary also point to the celebration of another festivity, the Inventio Osiridis.

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Some of them once a year, other rituals such as the dressing of the statue were held more often, even daily.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: All religious specialists, the ἱερεὺς, the ἀρχινεωκόρος, the ἱεραφόρος, are all men.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: In some other sanctuaries of Macedonia, there are some priests that held this office for life. This is not the case though in Thessalonica.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The fact that the inscriptions reveal both the titles of ἀρχινεωκόρος and νεωκόρος shows an hierarchy between them.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably one of the auxiliary structures next to the temples could have such a role but this is something that cannot be proven.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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